

Extension of Graphical Method of Reduction of Topological Matrices of Chemical Graphs

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Polyhedra, atom clusters (S_n , S_p , P_n), ligands of complexes with similar vertex atoms are some fertile fields besides many others where topology can play a useful role. Usual graphical reduction technique for writing topological matrices of the resulting subgraphs stops at a stage when symmetry is lost during the decomposition process. The process can, however, be continued with a proxy system of enforced symmetry until the stages of 1-vertex and 2-vertex graphs are obtained for an easy evaluation of eigenvalues which are either identical with or very close to the real ones.

Even in the face of the availability of PC's, capable of handling large matrices, the purpose of the present paper lies not only in its practical utility but also in its exhibition that the principle of graphical reduction holds greater potentiality than what has so far been exploited. Secondly, the method can serve as an extremely useful tool even for fairly big molecules or polyhedra.

THE topological eigenvalues of polyhedrons and nonconjugative systems, though having no apparent chemical and physical significances (except for π -systems), have nevertheless been found to play the roles of extremely important topological invariants correlating a host of molecular quantum properties. Their correlating potentiality strongly parallels those of some other topological indices. While their extensive correlation properties covering overlap integrals, binding energies, exchange integrals, molecular diamagnetic susceptibilities form a subject-matter of a separate communication¹, it is essential that one has an access to an easy way of evaluation of the topological eigenvalues of fairly large systems.

Earlier work had shown the existence of symmetry-based graphical decomposition methods equivalent to block or semiblock, diagonalisation of topological matrices of molecules, provided the latter possessed any two-fold or three-fold symmetry element such as C_2 , i , σ_v or C_3^{2-4} . The existence of higher-fold symmetry elements may also be exploited for a similar end. These graphical reduction methods follow certain recipes based either on symmetry considerations⁵ or on the mathematical reduction technique⁶ of symmetrical topological matrices.

Method 1

The graphical decomposition of a molecule enables splitting of the original topological matrix into smaller dimensional matrices with new vertex and edge weightages, facilitating easier evaluation of eigenvalues. It is to be noted that such decomposition is permissible when three symmetry features are satisfied with respect to C_2 , σ_v , or any other symmetry element which is being considered. Of these three features, one is the symmetry of the nuclear distribution under σ_v or the relevant symmetry operation, and the other two are the symmetries

in the distribution of edge-weightages and vertex-weightages, respectively. Continuation of further graphical decomposition of the already decomposed subgraphs of a molecule may be made, and it stops as soon as any of the symmetry conditions is lost in a newly decomposed subgraph of the molecule.

In the present paper, however, it is shown that one can proceed with graphical decomposition, even after the formal termination stage signalled by the loss of symmetry in the weightage distribution. What is done is that the graphically non-decomposable unit is substituted by a topological unit possessing three symmetry features, the chosen unit being a very slightly perturbed form of the real formally non-decomposable unit. The graphical decomposition may then continue leading to three-, two-, or even one-vertex graphs. The easily calculable topological eigenvalues of these very small units are either identical with or in very close neighbourhood of the actual eigenvalues of the original graphically non-decomposable unit. Before we proceed to illustrations, it will be convenient to consider the way of choosing the symmetrised proxy unit of the daughter subgraph for further graphical decomposition.

Let us consider a four-vertex decomposed unit (A) resulting from a previous stage of graphical decomposition having the following topology, with vertex- and edge-weightages appearing within () and { }, respectively. The four similar atoms, acting as vertices, are symbolised V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_4 . The topology (A) lacks symmetry in weightage

distribution, though a straightening of the chain (B) will ensure the presence of σ from the viewpoint

of nuclear distribution. This straightening is permissible since the topological matrix for the puckered form (A) and the straight form (B) remains the same, causing no change in eigenvalues.

The matrix for (A), [and also for (B)], is

$$T_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & \sqrt{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \sqrt{2} & 2 \end{pmatrix}$$

If we now enforce weightage symmetries (both vertex and edge) under σ_v in (B) by a process of averaging, the resulting hypothetical unit (C) will be

The corresponding matrix for (C) is,

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \frac{1+\sqrt{2}}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1+\sqrt{2}}{2} & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & \frac{1+\sqrt{2}}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1+\sqrt{2}}{2} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

i.e., $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1.207 & 0 & 0 \\ 1.207 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1.207 \\ 0 & 0 & 1.207 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = T_2$

The characters of both the original matrix T_1 and the new matrix T_2 are the same. However, the changes in two diagonal elements will cause a slight alteration in the eigenvalues of the two. The changes in the values will be slight since an important aspect in the shape of preservation of trace value has been maintained. The eigenvalues are also changed only in a marginal and secondary way by changes in some of the off-diagonal elements⁷. Hence one may conclude that eigenvalues of T_2 , i.e. (C), will be a close approximation to those of T_1 , i.e. (A) [or (B)].

Let us now consider an actual example, i.e. the anthracene molecule. In doing so, we should take

note of the following: (i) the general recipes^{4,6}, prescribed for formal decomposition as mentioned before, (ii) vertices are numbered 1, 2, 3 ... and the corresponding vertex-weightages appear within (); where no indication of vertex-weightage exists, the weightage is nil, and (iii) edge-weightages appear within { } alongside the edges of the molecular graph; where no edge-weightage is so indicated, the weightage value is unity.

Results and Discussion

Remembering the well-known prescriptions for the decomposition of graph as equivalent to block or semiblock diagonalisations respectively, let us consider the hydrogen suppressed graph (HSG) of the anthracene molecule where the carbon vertices are numbered in the parent graph (G) as well as in the decomposed daughter graphs (G^+ , G^-). The symbols G^+ , G^- represent symmetrised proxy graphs substituting for the real subgraphs G^+ , G^- respectively, where the latter no longer are symmetrically decomposable (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Eigenvalues of the topological matrix of anthracene molecule based on enforced symmetrisation (extension of McClelland's recipe).

It is thus seen that for the 14-vertex graph of the anthracene molecule, graphical decompositions would have ended at the third generation graphs (G^{++} , G^{+-} , G^{--} and G^{-+}). Of these, G^{++} and G^{-+} are each 4-vertex graphs and the remaining two 3-vertex each. These would have required solutions

of (4×4) - and (3×3) - dimensional secular determinants. On the other hand, enforced symmetrisation, resulting in slightly perturbed systems, yields six 2-vertex graphs of fourth generation: $[(G^{+++})', (G^{++-})', (G^{+-+})', (G^{+--})', (G^{-++})', (G^{-+-})', (G^{--+})']$ and two 1-vertex graphs $[(G^{+--}), (G^{---})]$, also of the fourth generation. The solutions of such small dimensional secular determinants are more readily effected.

The eigenvalues obtained by continuation of graphical decomposition accompanied with enforced symmetrisation and the true eigenvalues are given in Table 1. The method of such enforced symmetrisation is also applicable to polyhedra of atom clusters (same atoms) where King's recipe for decomposition is followed. One such illustration is provided in Fig. 2 for a regular trigonal bipyramid. For purposes of comparison, the eigenvalues of several polyhedral clusters are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Molecule/Species	True eigenvalues of topological matrix	Approximate eigenvalues of topological matrix based on enforced symmetrisation
Butane	$\pm 1.618, \pm 0.618$	$\pm 1.618, \pm 0.618$
Pentane	$\pm \sqrt{3}, \pm 1, 0$	$\pm 1.71, \pm 1, 0$
Hexane	$\pm 1.8, \pm 1.25, \pm 0.45$	$\pm 1.67, \pm 1.19, \pm 0.5$
Cyclopropene	$-2, 1, 1$	$-2, 1, 1$
Cyclobutadiene	$\pm 2, 0, 0$	$\pm 2, 0, 0$
Fulvene	$2.12, 1, 0.62, -0.25$	$2.06, 0.93, 0.62, -0.14$
Cyclobutene	$2.56, 0, -1, -1.56$	$2.56, 0, -1, -1.56$
3-Methylene-pena-1,4-diene	$\pm 1.93, \pm 0.52, \pm 1$	$\pm 1.93, \pm 0.52, \pm 1$
Benzyl radical	$\pm 2.1, \pm 1.26, \pm 1, 0$	$\pm 2.06, \pm 1.21, \pm 1, 0$
Allyl radical	$\pm \sqrt{2}, 0$	$\pm \sqrt{2}, 0$
Butadiene	$\pm 1.62, \pm 0.62$	$\pm 1.62, \pm 0.62$
Pentadienyl radical	$\pm \sqrt{3}, \pm 1, 0$	$\pm 1.71, \pm 1, 0$
Hexatriene	$\pm 1.8, \pm 1.25, \pm 0.45$	$\pm 1.69, \pm 1.17, \pm 0.5$
Dimethyl cyclobutene	$\pm 2.25, \pm 0.8, \pm 0.56$	$\pm 2.19, \pm 0.69, \pm 0.5$
Benzene	$\pm 2, \pm 1, \pm 1$	$\pm 2, \pm 1, \pm 1$
Naphthalene	$\pm 2.3, \pm 1.62, \pm 1.3, \pm 1, \pm 0.62$	$\pm 2.28, \pm 1.62, \pm 1.28, \pm 1, \pm 0.62$
Anthracene	$\pm 2.41, \pm 2, \pm 1.41, \pm 1.41, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 0.41$	$\pm 2.31, \pm 2, \pm 1.31, \pm 1.31, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 0.31$
Phenanthrene	$\pm 2.44, \pm 1.95, \pm 1.52, \pm 1.31, \pm 1.14, \pm 0.77, \pm 0.61$	$\pm 2.33, \pm 1.83, \pm 1.48, \pm 1.28, \pm 0.98, \pm 0.78, \pm 0.5$
1,4-Divinylbenzene	$\pm 2.21, \pm 1.68, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 0.54$	$\pm 1.98, \pm 1.67, \pm 1.17, \pm 1, \pm 0.48$
Diphenyl	$\pm 2.28, \pm 1.32, \pm 1.89, \pm 1, \pm 1, \pm 0.71$	$\pm 2.17, \pm 1.28, \pm 1.83, \pm 1.09, \pm 0.92, \pm 0.78$
Cyclopropenyl group	$2.17, -1.48, -1, 0.31$	$1.98, -1.48, -1, 0.5$

Before we conclude it is desirable to judge the reasonableness of tinkering the edge and vertex weightages of the non-decomposable subgraphs by a process of averaging. The net upshot is that the departures of eigenvalues obtained through enforced symmetrisation from the real ones are minimal, or nil, in cases where edge weightages (corresponding to

Fig. 2. Eigenvalues of trigonal bipyramidal cluster based on enforced symmetrisation (extension of King's recipe).

TABLE 2

Polyhedra	Point group	True eigenvalues of the topological matrix	Approximate eigenvalues on the basis of enforced symmetrisation
Tetrahedron	T_d	$3, -1, -1, -1$	$3, -1, -1, -1$
Trigonal bipyramid	D_{3h}	$0, -1, -1, -1.56, 3.65$	$0, -1, -1.11, -1.5, 3.61$
Square-pyramid	C_{4v}	$3.24, 0, 0, -1.24, -2$	$3.5, 0, 0, -1.5, -3$
Octahedron	O_h	$4, 0, 0, 0, -2, -2$	$4, 0, 0, 0, -2, -2$
Pentagonal pyramid	C_{5v}	$3.44, 0.61, 0.61, -1.45, -1.62, -1.62$	$3.52, 0.5, 0.5, -1.5, -1.61, -1.67$
Trigonal prism	D_{3h}	$3, 1, 0, 0, -2, -2$	$3, 1, 0, 0, -2, -2$
Pentagonal bipyramid	D_{5h}	$4.32, 0.62, 0.62, 0, -1.62, -1.62, -2.32$	$4.39, 0.5, 0.5, 0, -1.5, -1.88, -2.01$
Hexagonal pyramid	C_{6v}	$3.65, 1, 1, -1, -1, -1.65, -2.0$	$3.91, 1, 1, -1, -1.33, -1.58, -2.0$
Cube	O_h	$3, 1, 1, 1, -1, -1, -1, -3$	$3, 1, 1, 1, -1, -1, -1, -3$

off-diagonal elements) alone are overhauled. Errors in some of the eigenvalues tend to accumulate when

averaging of the vertex weightages (corresponding to diagonal matrix elements) is necessary.

This mathematical consequence on the final result is readily perceived when one remembers that in the general methods of obtaining approximate eigenvalues of matrices by diagonal approximation and the subsequent first order and second order corrections⁸, the diagonal matrix elements are kept intact, whereas the off-diagonal elements are freely dropped depending on the intended approximation. Hence to obtain the best possible results from enforced symmetrisation, it is necessary that one chooses such a symmetric division as will avoid, as far as possible, a prior averaging of vertex weightages. The latter, however, may not be entirely avoided in many cases when maximum simplification in the shape of lowering the dimensionality of the matrices is aimed.

It should be pointed out that in this extended graphical method involving a perturbation, a real degeneracy in actual case may show a non-degene-

rate result. Such results do occur, but not often (*cf.* trigonal bipyramid). This aspect can aptly be described as a minor flaw in view of the numerous advantages offered by such topological eigenvalues in the correlations of data on molecular properties¹.

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